

DataverseNO Working Group for Data Privacy

Mandate

Purpose

The purpose of the Working Group is to assist depositors and curators in assessing and documenting that data is in accordance with applicable legal regulations and research ethical principles and guidelines before it is potentially archived in DataverseNO.

Background

In recent years, DataverseNO has received datasets where it has been unclear whether the depositors/researchers had clarified whether open-access archiving of the data was in compliance with applicable legal regulations and research ethical principles and guidelines. An important criterion of the CoreTrustSeal certification for trustworthy data repositories is that they have solid policies, guidelines, and routines in place for the legal and ethical assessment of data to be archived. DataverseNO has an Accession Policy with fundamental requirements for data to be archived in the repository. In recent years, we have used a simple Word template to check basic privacy and ethical aspects of data. However, it has become evident that there is a need to revise and expand both the policy and the template, and to establish practical tools and resources to cover the full spectrum of data requiring protection, such as requirements related to biodiversity and health research.

Goals and Deliverables

The goal of the Working Group is to draft revised DataverseNO policies and guidelines, as well as create practical tools and resources for depositors and curators to assess and document that data requiring protection is in accordance with applicable legal regulations and research ethical principles and guidelines before the data is potentially published with open access in DataverseNO.

Key milestones in the Working Group's deliverables:

1. Map applicable legal regulations and research ethical principles and guidelines that are relevant for the archiving and access provisioning of research data.
2. Identify key criteria for necessary assessments.
3. Draft revisions of relevant DataverseNO policies and guidelines.
4. Implement the identified assessment criteria in appropriate tools and resources.
5. Develop a training plan and define how the tools and resources will be used.
6. Establish a plan for the maintenance and further development of the tools and resources.

Timeline

Time	Activity	Deliverable
February 2025	First group meeting	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Approval of the mandate • Allocation of roles and tasks, including group chair • Practical organization, including collaboration tools and meeting format and frequency
February to March 2025	Map applicable legal regulations and research ethics principles and guidelines relevant for the archiving and access provisioning of research data	Brief report identifying key legal regulations and research ethics principles
March to April 2025	Identify key criteria for necessary assessments	Brief report identifying key criteria
April to June 2025	Draft revisions of relevant DataverseNO policies and guidelines	Draft is ready for review by the DataverseNO board
August to October 2025	Implement the identified assessment criteria in appropriate tools and resources	First versions of tools and resources ready for testing
October to November 2025	Develop a training plan and define how the tools and resources will be used	The plan is ready.
October to November 2025	Establish a plan for the maintenance and further development of the tools and resources	The maintenance and development plan is ready.
November 2025	Launch tools, resources, and training plan	Presentation at the DataverseNO User Forum meeting

Participation, Roles, Responsibilities, and Resource Requirements

Participants in the Working Group are expected to contribute effort and time to deliverables and tasks. The Working Group chair(s) shall allocate sufficient time to ensure that the Working Group delivers the expected results in accordance with the timeline.

To achieve the best possible outcome, it is important that Working Group include participants from as many partner institutions as possible.

Practical Organization

Practical organization and distribution of roles and responsibilities will be decided at the first group meeting in February 2025.

Version log

Action	Version	Date	Involved
First draft created.	0.1	22.01.2025	Repository management
Mandate approved.	1.0	17.02.2025	Working Group